

Software Reuse File

Global Fish Tracking System

FOR ESA and Starion
BY Development Seed

VERSION 1.1
DATE April 15, 2025

Dependencies

This section constitutes the Software Reuse File for the Global Fish Tracking Software (GFTS) DestinE Platform use case. The list will continuously be updated and expanded as the project progresses.

Python

The first level python dependencies are listed in the following file on GitHub.

https://github.com/destination-earth/DestinE_ESA_GFTS/blob/main/.binder/environment.yml

Javascript

The first level javascript dependencies are listed in the following file on GitHub.

<https://github.com/developmentseed/gfts/blob/main/package.json>